

Three rice varieties – IR20, IR36, and Dular – were grown in both types of units. ET data were collected from the 2 units from 15 days after planting until flowering. There was good agreement of data obtained from each type of unit. When graphed, the distribution of data points along a 1:1 line indicated that both microlysimeters are reliable and accurate for ET measurement in wetland rice fields.

The table shows an example of ET rates for the 3 cultivars and pan

Evapotranspiration rate at maximum tillering growth stage on 1 clear day for 3 cultivars of rice grown at IRRI in the 1978 dry and wet seasons.

Date	Season	Evapotranspiration (mm/day)			Av pan evaporation (mm/day)	Solar radiation (cal/cm ² per day)
		IR36	IR20	Dular		
13 Apr	Dry	10.0	9.0	8.2	8.8	663
25 Sep	Wet	5.7	4.3	7.8	4.8	571
19 Dec	Wet	4.2	4.3	6.2	4.2	476

evaporation and solar radiation values on 3 clear days at about the maximum tillering stage in the 1978 dry and wet seasons.

Simple to fabricate and maintain the

microlysimeters can be made locally and handled easily. The microlysimeter principle might also be applied to ecological studies of water use by non-crop aquatic and semi-aquatic species. ■

Soil and crop management

Role of balanced fertilizers in increasing farmers' rice yields and profits

M. Zahidul Hoque and Md. Akhter Hossain Khan, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca., Bangladesh

To examine the potential of using recommended levels of balanced fertilizers, an experiment was conducted in a farmer's field at the BRRI cropping systems research site at Laskarchala in 1979 aus. The variety Chandina (BR1)

was used; the crop was transplanted, with supplemental irrigation. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Treatments consisted of 4 levels of fertilizer application: the farmer's level (26-47-0 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha), the recommended level for N + the farmers' level of P₂O₅ (80-47-0 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha), the recommended level for N-P₂O₅-K₂O (80-60-40 kg/ha), and the recommended level for N-P₂O₅-K₂O plus sulfur as SO₄ (80-60-40-34 kg/ha).

The yield was highest from the recommended level for NPK plus sulfur (4.3 t/ha), but it did not differ significantly from the treatment without sulfur (3.9 t/ha) (see table).

Replacing the farmer's level of N only with the recommended level significantly increased grain yield (3.3 t/ha vs 2.6 t/ha). Economic analysis of the extra costs and returns over the farmer's level indicated that investing an extra US\$16.57–31.53/ha could bring an extra net return of US\$129.00–372.28/ha. ■

Agroeconomic evaluation of extra nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and sulfur over the farmer's level of management in the 1979 aus at the Laskarchala BRRI Cropping Systems Research Site.

Treatment	Fertilizer rate (kg/ha)				Yield ^a (t/ha)	Added yield over farmer's level (t/ha)	Value of added yield (US\$/ha)	Cost of added inputs (US\$/ha)	Added profit over farmer's level (US\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	SO ₄						
1 ^b	26	47	0	0	2.6 c	–	–	–	–	–
2	80	47	0	0	3.3 b	0.6	145.58	16.57	129.01	7.7
3 ^c	80	60	40	0	3.9 a	1.3	308.51	26.63	281.88	10.5
4	80	60	40	34	4.3 a	1.7	403.80	31.53	372.28	11.8

^aCV = 6%. Mean yields with a common letter did not differ significantly at the 1% level. ^bFarmer's level. ^cRecommended level.

Varietal reaction of rice to age of seedlings transplanted in alkali soil

S. S. Singh, staff member, and Singh R. Deosharan, graduate student, Agronomy Department, Allahabad Agricultural Institute, Allahabad, U.P., India

An experiment conducted on an alkali soil (pH 8.2, ESP: 15.47%, and EC: 0.48 mmho/cm at 25°C) in 1977–78 kharif studied the effects of transplanting

seedlings of different ages. The split-plot design had varieties in the main plot and seedling age in the subplot. Fertilizer was applied at 120 kg N/ha (60 kg basal, 30 kg 20 days after transplanting [DT], and 30 kg at 40 DT irrespective of growth stage), 60 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 80 kg K₂O/ha as basal. Three healthy seedlings were transplanted in each hill.

The table shows that the period

required for establishment was not greatly influenced by the age of seedlings at transplanting. However, seedlings older than 25 days were established 1 or 2 days earlier. The time from panicle emergence to maturity generally was shorter in the short-duration variety Bala than in the medium-duration Ratna and the long-duration Sona. But in all three varieties, the time was shorter in seedlings

Effect of seedling age at transplanting on establishment, maturity, grain yield, and straw-grain ratio of 3 rice varieties, 1977-78 kharif, Allahabad, India.^a

Age of seedlings (days)	Establishment (DT)			Time between PE & maturity (days)			Maturity (days)			Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw-grain ratio		
	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S
25	6	6	6	35	48	50	109	128	130	2.7	2.6	2.4	1.18	1.26	1.19
35	5	5	5	30	45	35	117	130	132	2.0	2.8	2.8	1.31	1.30	1.42
45	5	5	5	28	40	37	120	133	135	2.0	1.9	2.1	1.26	1.26	1.37
55	5	4	4	22	30	31	131	135	141	0.8	0.8	1.3	1.21	1.19	1.21

^aDT = days after transplanting. B = Bala. R = Ratna. S = Sona. PE = panicle emergence. Grain yield: highly significant for seedling-age treatment. LSD for seedling-age treatments: 0.381. LSD for variety treatments: 0.258.

that were older at planting. In contrast, seedlings that were transplanted at an older age matured later. That could account for the greater setback at different growth stages of older seedlings. Relatively older seedlings of Ratna and Sona gave the highest grain yields when transplanted at 35 days but gave lower

yields when transplanted later. The straw-grain ratio, which was highest in 35-day-old seedlings, decreased in older seedlings, which grew and developed poorly.

It may be concluded that rice seedlings should be transplanted in alkali soils between the ages of 25 and 35 days. If

transplanted earlier, the seedlings may die; if transplanted later, they will yield poorly. The finding could be due to the higher concentration of soluble salts that results in the higher mortality of seedlings planted when between 21 and 25 days old. Thus, the older seedlings do better in saline alkali soils. ■

Potassium chloride pretreatment on rice seeds

Syed Nazeer Peeran and S.

Natanasabapathy, Soil Science Section, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur 602025, Chingleput district, Tamil Nadu, India

A field trial was conducted to determine the efficiency and response of rice seedlings to nutrients available in the soil. The variety ADT31 was used in a two-replication split-plot design.

The main plot treatments were M1 -- green leaf manure at 5 t/ha; M2 -- M1 + superphosphate at 250 kg/ha; M3 -- M2 + blue-green algae at 25 kg/ha; M4 -- nitrogen placed at 75 kg N/ha; and M5 -- control (no manure).

The subplot treatments were S1 --

Grain yield of fertilized rice plants and pretreated rice seeds. Tamil Nadu, India.

Main plot	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control	Subplot	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control
M1	3.6	116	S1	3.1	100
M2	3.7	120	S2	4.2	135
M3	3.5	114	S3	3.8	121
M4	4.2	134	S4	3.6	115
M5	3.1	100	S5	3.3	106
			S6	3.7	119
<i>'F' test</i>					
SE	122.0			45.1	
LSD	0.480			0.131	

control; S2 -- potassium chloride 1% (seed soaking); S3 -- manganese sulfate 8% (seed soaking); S4 -- ferrous sulfate 8% (seed soaking); S5 -- diammonium phosphate 4% (sprouted seed treatment); and S6 -- zinc sulfate 4% (sprouted seed treatment).

Among the main plot treatments, M4 gave a 34% higher yield than the control (see table).

Among the subplot treatments, S2 was significantly superior treatments and gave the highest grain yield, 35.0% over the control. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Performance of improved agricultural practices for dryland rice production in Sierra Leone

R. A. D. Jones, I. C. Mahapatra, and S. R. Bapat, Rice Research Station, Rokupr, Sierra Leone

Trials were conducted for the past 3 years on rice in farmers' fields under

Feb 27/23/80

dryland ecology at sites across Sierra Leone to determine:

1. If permanent cultivation can replace the bush fallow-rice system of traditional cultivation.
2. If improved cultivation methods can increase the yields of traditional rice varieties.
3. The benefit-cost ratio due to

fertilizer application.

Upland farmers in this part of Africa every year clear the bush from a new site and abandon that site after one rice crop or a crop of groundnut, cassava, or both, and return to the same site 8-10 years later. The fallow period has been reduced to 4-5 years in some parts of Sierra Leone.